

Search Strategies: Opioid Time to Death (IMPACCT)

Date: 06-08-14

CINAHL1981-present

Search

01-08-14

S27 S3 AND S8 AND S26

S26 S19 OR S25

S25 S20 OR S21 OR S22 OR S23 OR S24

S24 TX("prolong* survival" or "longer survival" or "live longer")

S23 TX(time* n5 (death* or survival or life or longevity or mortality))

S22 TX(survival n3 (short* or reduc* or duration or length))

S21 TX((die* or dying or death) n3 (quick* or rapid* or sudden* or hast* or prompt or brisk or hurried or swift or accerlat*))

S20 TI(life n3 shorten*) OR AB(life n3 shorten*)

S19 S14 AND S18

S18 S15 OR S16 OR S17

S17 TI "long period" OR AB "long period"

S16 TI((alive or dead) n3 (month or months))or AB((alive or dead) n3 (month or months))

S15 (MH "Time Factors" or MH "Time")

S14 S9 OR S10 OR S11 OR S12 OR S13

S13 TI (mortality or death or deaths) or AB (mortality or death or deaths)

S12 (MH "Life Expectancy" or MH "Longevity")

S11 TI (survival or "life expectancy" or longevity or "life span") or AB (survival or "life expectancy" or longevity or "life span")

S10 (MH "Survival Analysis" or MH "Kaplan-Meier Estimator" or MH "Cox Proportional Hazards Model")

S9 (MH "Mortality" or MH "Cause of Death" or MH "Fatal Outcome" or MH "Hospital Mortality" or MH "mortality" or MH "Survival")

S8 S4 OR S5 OR S6 OR S7

S7 TI (opioid* or opiate*) or AB (opioid* or opiate*)

S6 TX(Buprenorphine or Codeine or diamorphine or Dextropropoxyphene or Fentanyl or Heroin or Hydrocodone or Hydromorphone or Methadone or Morphine or Opium or Oxycodone or Oxymorphone or Tramadol)

S5 (MH "Narcotics+")

S4 (MH "Analgesics, Opioid+")

S3 S1 AND S2

S2 (MH "Neoplasms+") AND ((cancer* or carcinoma* or metastas* or neoplasm* or tumor* or tumour* or malignan*))

S1 (MH "Neoplasms+")

ClinicalTrials.gov 2000-present

Search

31-07-14

Cancer and opioids or opiates or opioid or opiate

Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials : Issue 6 of 12, June 2014

Search

31-07-14

#1 MeSH descriptor: [Neoplasms] explode all trees

#2 (cancer* or carcinoma* or metastas* or neoplasm* or tumor* or tumour* or malignan*):ti,ab,kw
(Word variations have been searched)

#3 #1 or #2

#4 MeSH descriptor: [Analgesics, Opioid] explode all trees

#5 MeSH descriptor: [Opiate Alkaloids] explode all trees

#6 Buprenorphine or Codeine or diamorphine or Dextropropoxyphene or Fentanyl or Heroin or Hydrocodone or Hydromorphone or Methadone or Morphine or Opium or Oxycodone or Oxymorphone or Tramadol:ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)

#7 opioid* or opiate*

#8 #4 or #5 or #6 or #7

#9 MeSH descriptor: [Cause of Death] this term only

#10 MeSH descriptor: [Mortality] this term only

#11 MeSH descriptor: [Fatal Outcome] this term only

#12 MeSH descriptor: [Hospital Mortality] this term only

#13 MeSH descriptor: [Mortality, Premature] this term only

#14 MeSH descriptor: [Survival Rate] this term only

#15 MeSH descriptor: [Survival Analysis] this term only

#16 MeSH descriptor: [Disease-Free Survival] this term only

- #17 MeSH descriptor: [Kaplan-Meier Estimate] this term only
- #18 survival or "life expectancy" or longevity or "life span" or mortality or death or deaths:ti,ab,kw
(Word variations have been searched)
- #19 MeSH descriptor: [Longevity] this term only
- #20 MeSH descriptor: [Life Expectancy] this term only
- #21 #9 or #10 or #11 or #12 or #13 or #14 or #15 or #16 or #17 or #18 or #19 or #20
- #22 MeSH descriptor: [Time Factors] this term only
- #23 MeSH descriptor: [Time] this term only
- #24 ((alive or dead) near/3 (month or months)):ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)
- #25 "long period"
- #26 #22 or #23 or #24 or #25
- #27 #21 and #26
- #28 (life near/3 shorten*):ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)
- #29 ((die* or dying or death) near/3 (quick* or rapid* or sudden* or hast* or prompt or brisk or hurried or swift or accerlat*)):ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)
- #30 (survival near/3 (short* or reduc* or duration or length))
- #31 (time* near/5 (death* or survival or life or longevity or mortality))
- #32 "prolong* survival" or "longer survival" or "live longer":ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)
- #33 #28 or #29 or #30 or #31 or #32
- #34 #27 or #33
- #35 #3 and #8 and #34

Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews : Issue 7 of 12, July 2014

Search

31-07-14

Same as Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials : Issue 6 of 12, June 2014

Database of Abstracts of Reviews of Effect : Issue 2 of 4, April 2014

Search

31-07-14

Same as Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials : Issue 6 of 12, June 2014

NHS Economic Evaluation Database : Issue 2 of 4, April 2014

Search

31-07-14

Same as Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials : Issue 6 of 12, June 2014

Embase Classic+Embase <1947 to 2014 July 31>

Search

01-08-14

- 1 exp neoplasm/ (3645732)
- 2 (cancer* or carcinoma* or metastas* or neoplasm* or tumor* or tumour* or malignan*).tw. (2992931)
- 3 1 or 2 [Broad cancer] (4180970)
- 4 exp *narcotic analgesic agent/ (129214)
- 5 exp *opiate/ (19044)
- 6 (Buprenorphine or Codeine or diamorphine or Dextropropoxyphene or Fentanyl or Heroin or Hydrocodone or Hydromorphone or Methadone or Morphine or Opium or Oxycodone or Oxymorphone or Tramadol).tw. [Important drugs highlighted by Jason] (107868)
- 7 opioid*.tw. (72231)
- 8 opiate*.tw. (27991)
- 9 or/4-8 [Opiates or Opioids] (213111)
- 10 *mortality/ or *premature mortality/ or *cancer mortality/ (65861)
- 11 exp *survival/ (56023)
- 12 survival.tw. (811177)
- 13 *longevity/ (6477)
- 14 ("life expectancy" or longevity).tw. (48872)
- 15 "life span".tw. (23420)
- 16 *life expectancy/ (5432)
- 17 mortality.tw. (657093)
- 18 (death or deaths).tw. (751540)
- 19 or/10-18 [death or survival] (1920063)
- 20 *time/ (4872)
- 21 ((alive or dead) adj3 (month or months)).tw. (3194)
- 22 "long period".tw. (15261)
- 23 or/20-22 [time] (23311)

- 24 19 and 23 [death or survival and time] (3989)
- 25 (life adj3 shorten*).tw. (3361)
- 26 ((die* or dying or death) adj3 (quick* or rapid* or sudden* or hast* or prompt or brisk or hurried or swift or accerlat*)).tw. (56172)
- 27 (survival adj3 (short* or reduc* or duration or length)).tw. (41715)
- 28 (time* adj5 (death* or survival or life or longevity or mortality)).tw. (111529)
- 29 "prolong* survival".tw. (17565)
- 30 "longer survival".tw. (7199)
- 31 "live longer".tw. (1921)
- 32 or/26-31 [time to death phrases] (221285)
- 33 24 or 32 [death or survival and time or time to death phrases] (224578)
- 34 3 and 9 and 33 (349)
- 35 exp animals/ not (exp animals/ and exp humans/) (4627602)
- 36 34 not 35 (322)

Ovid MEDLINE(R) <1946 to July Week 4 2014>

Search

31-07-14

- 1 exp neoplasms/ (2577521)
- 2 (cancer* or carcinoma* or metastas* or neoplasm* or tumor* or tumour* or malignan*).tw. (2104215)
- 3 1 or 2 [Broad cancer] (2976521)
- 4 exp Analgesics, Opioid/ (92518)
- 5 exp Opiate Alkaloids/ (75800)
- 6 (Buprenorphine or Codeine or diamorphine or Dextropropoxyphene or Fentanyl or Heroin or Hydrocodone or Hydromorphone or Methadone or Morphine or Opium or Oxycodone or Oxymorphone or Tramadol).tw. [Important drugs highlighted by Jason] (75429)
- 7 opioid*.tw. (54765)
- 8 opiate*.tw. (21367)
- 9 or/4-8 [Opiates or Opioids] (158066)
- 10 Mortality/ or Cause of Death/ or Fatal Outcome/ or Hospital Mortality/ or Mortality, Premature/ or Survival Rate/ (256691)
- 11 survival analysis/ or disease-free survival/ or kaplan-meier estimate/ or proportional hazards models/ (187941)
- 12 survival.tw. (559797)
- 13 Longevity/ (15371)

- 14 ("life expectancy" or longevity).tw. (35652)
- 15 "life span".tw. (17472)
- 16 Life Expectancy/ (14066)
- 17 mortality.tw. (436851)
- 18 (death or deaths).tw. (515013)
- 19 or/10-18 [death or survival] (1450236)
- 20 Time Factors/ (1009180)
- 21 Time/ (10270)
- 22 ((alive or dead) adj3 (month or months)).tw. (2132)
- 23 "long period".tw. (8686)
- 24 or/20-23 [time] (1028080)
- 25 19 and 24 [death or survival and time] (126440)
- 26 (life adj3 shorten*).tw. (2114)
- 27 ((die* or dying or death) adj3 (quick* or rapid* or sudden* or hast* or prompt or brisk or hurried or swift or accerlat*)).tw. (38723)
- 28 (survival adj3 (short* or reduc* or duration or length)).tw. (29184)
- 29 (time* adj5 (death* or survival or life or longevity or mortality)).tw. (74076)
- 30 "prolong* survival".tw. (12264)
- 31 "longer survival".tw. (4899)
- 32 "live longer".tw. (1306)
- 33 or/26-32 [time to death phrases] (152121)
- 34 25 or 33 [death or survival and time or time to death phrases] (262220)
- 35 3 and 9 and 34 (297)
- 36 exp animals/ not humans.sh. (3972897)
- 37 35 not 36 (261)

Ovid MEDLINE(R) In-Process & Other Non-Indexed Citations

Search

30-07-14

- 1 exp neoplasms/ (16)
- 2 (cancer* or carcinoma* or metastas* or neoplasm* or tumor* or tumour* or malignan*).tw. (143771)
- 3 1 or 2 [Broad cancer] (143775)
- 4 exp Analgesics, Opioid/ (1)
- 5 exp Opiate Alkaloids/ (0)

- 6 (Buprenorphine or Codeine or diamorphine or Dextropropoxyphene or Fentanyl or Heroin or Hydrocodone or Hydromorphone or Methadone or Morphine or Opium or Oxycodone or Oxymorphone or Tramadol).tw. [Important drugs highlighted by Jason] (4392)
- 7 opioid*.tw. (3647)
- 8 opiate*.tw. (734)
- 9 or/4-8 [Opiates or Opioids] (7004)
- 10 Mortality/ or Cause of Death/ or Fatal Outcome/ or Hospital Mortality/ or Mortality, Premature/ or Survival Rate/ (0)
- 11 survival analysis/ or disease-free survival/ or kaplan-meier estimate/ or proportional hazards models/ (1)
- 12 survival.tw. (41161)
- 13 Longevity/ (0)
- 14 ("life expectancy" or longevity).tw. (3206)
- 15 "life span".tw. (948)
- 16 Life Expectancy/ (0)
- 17 mortality.tw. (36584)
- 18 (death or deaths).tw. (35801)
- 19 or/10-18 [death or survival] (99759)
- 20 Time Factors/ (2)
- 21 Time/ (0)
- 22 ((alive or dead) adj3 (month or months)).tw. (78)
- 23 "long period".tw. (1133)
- 24 or/20-23 [time] (1213)
- 25 19 and 24 [death or survival and time] (102)
- 26 (life adj3 shorten*).tw. (142)
- 27 ((die* or dying or death) adj3 (quick* or rapid* or sudden* or hast* or prompt or brisk or hurried or swift or accerlat*)).tw. (2294)
- 28 (survival adj3 (short* or reduc* or duration or length)).tw. (2010)
- 29 (time* adj5 (death* or survival or life or longevity or mortality)).tw. (5025)
- 30 "prolong* survival".tw. (690)
- 31 "longer survival".tw. (322)
- 32 "live longer".tw. (118)
- 33 or/26-32 [time to death phrases] (9971)
- 34 25 or 33 [death or survival and time or time to death phrases] (10063)
- 35 3 and 9 and 34 (15)

Web of Science Conference Proceedings Citation Index Science (CPCI-SSH) 1990-present

Search

31-07-14

(cancer and opioid*) AND TOPIC: ((death or mortality or survival))

WHO ICTRP Trials Register 2004-present

Search

31-07-14

Cancer and opioids or opioid or opiate or opiates